

Synthesis, spectral characterization and antimicrobial studies of some new binuclear complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} Schiff base

D. Prakash*, C. Kumar, S. Prakash, A. K. Gupta and K. R. R. P. Singh

Department of Chemistry, Patna University, Patna-800 005, Bihar, India

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Abstract : Heterobinuclear alkali metal complexes of Cu^{II} or Ni^{II} with Schiff base derived from condensation of 1,2-propylenediamine with *o*-hydroxyacetophenone in 1 : 2 molar ratio have been synthesized. They were characterized by elemental analysis, IR spectra, UV-Visible spectral analysis, magnetic and molar conductance measurements. The synthesized binuclear Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes of Schiff base are found to have square planar geometry. No change in the stereochemistry of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} complexes was observed after formation of adduct with the alkali metal salts of the organic acids. The antimicrobial activity of some of the heterobinuclear complexes are assayed which demonstrated inhibitory effect against some bacteria and fungi.

Keywords : Heterobinuclear alkali metal complexes, IR, UV-Visible spectra, antimicrobial studies, MIC.

Introduction

There has been considerable recent interest in the preparation of binuclear complexes. In majority of binucleating ligands the two donor sites are equivalent and in most of their complexes the two metal ions are similar^{1,2}. In the present communication we report the synthesis and antimicrobial activities of complexes involving Cu^{II} or Ni^{II} metal ions and the Schiff base (PA, constituting 1,2-propylenediamine and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone) with the alkali metal salt of the organic acids having the general formula M_aPA.M_bL, where M_a = Cu^{II} or Ni^{II}, PA = *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(2-hydroxyacetophenonimate), M_b = Li, Na or K; L = deprotonated *o*-nitrophenol (ONP), 2,4-dinitrophenol (DNP), 2,4,6-trinitrophenol (TNP), 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (1N2N).

Results and discussion

The Cu^{II} or Ni^{II} metal chelates and their adducts with organic acid salt of alkali metals are coloured solid and are stable in air at room temperature (Table 1). The adducts are generally soluble in methanol, acetone, benzene and dimethyl formamide (DMF) but insoluble in water. Molar conductivities of complexes in DMF at 30 (±0.5) °C and at concentration of 10⁻³ M (Table 1) show low value (0.8–6.2 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹), which suggest the non-electrolytic nature⁵ of the complexes.

The CuPA, NiPA and their binuclear alkali metal complexes show infrared bands in the region 1529–1597 cm⁻¹ (Table 2). These bands arise due to C–O stretching in these compounds rather than C=N stretching. The position of infrared bands near 1530 cm⁻¹ arising in various transition metal Schiff base complexes has been assigned to C–O stretching by several authors^{6–11}. The mononuclear metal complexes CuPA and NiPA exhibit ν_{C–O} str. (phenolic) at 1530 and 1529 cm⁻¹ respectively which shifts toward higher energy side (with few exceptions) on complexation with alkali metal salts of organic acids indicating the coordination through the phenolic O-atom⁷. The shift is expected due to ring current arising from electron delocalisation in chelating ring. Splitting in few complexes indicate the influence of C–O bond of the alkali metal salt of organic acid. The bands in the far infrared region i.e. 463–480 and 521–593 cm⁻¹ in the binuclear complexes may be assigned to M–N and M–O modes respectively. The M–N vibrations as expected appear at lower frequencies than M–O vibrations since M–O bond is more ionic than M–N bond⁸. The data in the far infrared region suggest the coordination of oxygen-atom of phenolic group of Schiff base and oxygen-atom of -NO, -NO₂ etc. to alkali metal salt of organic acids in all the binuclear complexes.

The bands in the UV-Vis spectra (Table 2) for the

Table 1. Analytical, magnetic and molar conductance data of the complexes

Compd. M _a PA.M _b L	Colour	Melt.(m) Dec.(d)/ Trans.(t) temp. (°C)	Molar cond. (Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹)	μ _{eff} (B.M.)	Analysis (%) :					Yield (%)
					Found (Calcd.)					
					C	H	N	M _a	M _b	
CuPA.LiONP	Red	295m	0.9	-	57.90 (58.08)	4.58 (4.65)	8.07 (8.13)	12.19 (12.29)	1.31 (1.36)	75.02
CuPA.NaONP	Red	296m	1.0	-	56.25 (56.34)	4.43 (4.51)	7.74 (7.89)	11.85 (11.92)	4.28 (4.32)	76.02
CuPA.KONP	Red	298m	0.8	1.78	54.56 (54.69)	4.31 (4.38)	7.55 (7.66)	11.52 (11.58)	7.06 (7.11)	75.21
CuPA.LiDNP	Purple	280d	3.4	1.76	53.35 (53.43)	4.01 (4.10)	9.89 (9.97)	11.25 (11.31)	1.19 (1.25)	75.69
CuPA.NaDNP	Greenish brown	251m	3.6	-	51.82 (51.95)	3.83 (3.98)	9.65 (9.70)	10.98 (11.00)	3.92 (3.98)	71.43
CuPA.KDNP	Brown	253m	5.5	-	50.50 (50.55)	3.82 (3.88)	9.38 (9.44)	10.62 (10.70)	6.51 (6.57)	68.24
CuPA.LiTNP	Golden brown	205m	5.6	-	49.36 (49.46)	3.54 (3.63)	11.46 (11.54)	10.42 (10.47)	1.11 (1.15)	74.20
CuPA.NaTNP	Golden brown	258m	6.0	1.73	48.12 (48.19)	3.47 (3.53)	11.11 (11.24)	10.13 (10.20)	3.62 (3.69)	74.70
CuPA.KTNP	Orange yellow	255m	6.2	-	46.85 (46.99)	3.37 (3.45)	10.88 (10.96)	9.91 (9.95)	6.02 (6.11)	72.44
CuPA.Li1N2N	Yellowish brown	274m	0.8	1.98	63.18 (63.22)	4.66 (4.72)	7.56 (7.63)	11.48 (11.53)	1.23 (1.27)	72.66
CuPA.Na1N2N	Brown	273m	0.9	-	61.39 (61.43)	4.52 (4.59)	7.38 (7.41)	11.16 (11.21)	4.02 (4.06)	75.90
CuPA.K1N2N	Brown	271m	0.9	-	59.61 (59.74)	4.41 (4.46)	7.15 (7.21)	10.86 (10.90)	6.64 (6.70)	77.25
NiPA.LiONP	Brick red	> 300	1.8	-	58.55 (58.63)	4.50 (4.69)	8.16 (8.21)	11.38 (11.47)	1.31 (1.37)	77.19
NiPA.NaONP	Red	> 300	2.1	-	56.78 (56.85)	4.50 (4.55)	7.88 (7.96)	11.01 (11.12)	4.27 (4.36)	73.43
NiPA.KONP	Brick red	> 300	1.2	-	55.05 (55.18)	4.35 (4.41)	7.66 (7.72)	10.70 (10.80)	7.08 (7.17)	73.57
NiPA.LiTNP	Yellowish orange	260md	2.2	-	49.78 (49.86)	3.55 (3.66)	11.52 (11.63)	9.56 (9.76)	1.08 (1.16)	68.56
NiPA.NaTNP	Yellowish orange	281md	1.2	-	48.53 (48.57)	3.48 (3.56)	11.28 (11.33)	9.52 (9.50)	3.68 (3.72)	72.85
NiPA.KTNP	Yellowish orange	270d	1.3	-	47.25 (47.34)	3.41 (3.47)	10.90 (11.05)	9.15 (9.26)	6.03 (6.15)	69.43
NiPA.Li1N2N	Golden brown	265d	0.8	-	63.65 (63.77)	4.68 (4.76)	7.69 (7.70)	10.71 (10.76)	1.21 (1.28)	75.59
NiPA.Na1N2N	Reddish brown	282d	0.5	-	61.85 (61.95)	4.55 (4.63)	7.41 (7.48)	10.36 (10.45)	4.01 (4.09)	78.33
NiPA.K1N2N	Greenish brown	268d	1.1	-	60.15 (60.24)	4.41 (4.50)	7.14 (7.27)	10.11 (10.16)	6.68 (6.75)	74.00

where, m – sharp melting point, d – decomposition temperature, md – melting with decomposition and t – transition temperature.

Table 2. Spectral data of metal chelate and their metal complexes

Compd	Infrared spectra (cm ⁻¹)			UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectra (nm)
	$\nu(\text{C-O})$ phenolic	$\nu(\text{M-O})$	$\nu(\text{M-N})$	
CuPA	1530	592, 523	462	230, 266, 347, 653
CuPA KONP	1531	593, 527	463	232, 266, 347, 653
CuPA LiDNP	1531	527	470	219, 239, 264, 348, 653
CuPA NaTNP	1590	565, 525	480	231, 266, 348, 653
CuPA Li1N2N	1531, 1464	527	465	220, 236, 266, 348, 652
NiPA	1529	569, 527	485	242, 321, 392
NiPA NaONP	1568, 1485	530	470	244, 321, 392, 653
NiPA LiTNP	1568, 1464	521	470	210, 242, 344, 654
NiPA K1N2N	1597, 1531	571, 528	480	221, 250, 290, 382, 652

chelate neutral complexes of Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} metals of ligand Schiff bases of 1,2-propylenediamine and *o*-hydroxyacetophenone were observed at 230, 266 nm and 242, 321 nm respectively, which indicate $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in aromatic ring and C=N chromophore. Similarly, in the UV-Visible spectra for the adducts of CuPA and those for the adducts of NiPA bands are found in the region 219–348 and 210–392 nm respectively indicating $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition. For them, bands around 653 nm indicate charge transfer or *d-d* transition. The magnetic moment values around ~ 1.73 – 1.98 B.M. also support the square planar geometry for the transition metals in the adducts.

From the above discussion of the IR spectra, magnetic properties and electronic spectral studies of the adducts, it is concluded that the bonding between the *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(2-hydroxyacetophenoniminato)metal(II) complex (M_aPA) and the alkali metal salt of the organic acids (M_bL) is most likely to occur by dative bonding via two phenolic oxygen atoms of the ligand. The structure and bonding of the newly prepared complexes with general formula $[M_aPA.M_bL]$ may be suggested (Fig. 1).

Antimicrobial activity :

The synthesized heterobinuclear complexes were tested for their antibacterial activity against bacteria viz. *Escherichia coli*, *Staphylococcus aureus* and antifungal activity against fungus viz. *Candida albicans* in the solvent DMF in the concentration range 25–200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$. The Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC) results of

e.g.

Fig. 1. Suggested structure for the complexes, where M_aPA = CuPA or NiPA, M_b = Li, Na or K, and L = deprotonated 2,4-dinitrophenol, 2,4,6-trinitrophenol or 1-nitroso-2-naphthol

some of the complexes are shown in Table 3. From the MIC results we conclude that most of the adducts of NiPA and CuPA show great degree of activity at higher concentration against test organisms viz. bacteria *E. coli*, *S. aureus* and fungi *C. albicans* and as the concentration of these adducts increases antimicrobial activity increases gradually.

Table 3. MIC values of some of the adducts of M_aPA with alkali metal salt of organic acids

Compd.	Concen. ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$)	Percentage inhibition		
		<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>C. albicans</i>
NiPA.Li1N1P	200	85-90	85-90	50-55
	100	85-90	85-90	50-55
	50	85-90	85-90	50-55
	25	50-55	50-55	0
NiPA.K1N2N	200	100	100	100
	100	100	100	100
	50	100	100	100
	25	85-90	85-90	85-90
CuPA.Na1N1P	200	0	50-55	50-55
	100	0	50-55	50-55
	50	0	0	0
	25	0	0	0
CuPA.Li1N2N	200	100	100	100
	100	100	85-90	100
	50	100	50-55	85-90
	25	85-90	50-55	50-55

Experimental

Chemicals of A.R. grade have been used for synthesizing the complexes. IR spectra were recorded on FTIR spectrophotometer, Shimadzu model-8201 PC in KBr phase. Electronic spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer Lambda-15 UVB Vis spectrophotometer. Melting point of the compounds were determined on electrical tempo T-1150 melting point apparatus. Molar conductivities were measured with the help of Systronic digital direct conductivity meter-306. Magnetic measurements were performed on Gouy balance. The C, H, N were analyzed on Heraeus B6450 CHN elemental analyzer. Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} ions have been estimated by complexometric EDTA titrations and the estimation of alkali metal ions (Li⁺, Na⁺ and K⁺) were carried out by flame photometric method.

Synthetic procedures :

Preparation of Schiff base of o-hydroxyacetophenone and 1,2-propylenediamine :

The Schiff base of *o*-hydroxyacetophenone and 1,2-

propylenediamine were prepared by refluxing the aldehyde and diamine in 2 : 1 molar proportion in ethanol for 10 min. The yellow coloured Schiff base was precipitated out. It was filtered off, washed thoroughly with ethanol and dried in electric oven at 80 °C and finally kept in desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Preparation of complexes involving Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} metal ions with Schiff base (PA) :

A solution of copper(II) acetate hydrate (2.0 g) or nickel(II) acetate tetrahydrate (2.5 g) in ethanol (15 ml) was added slowly with stirring to a hot solution of the Schiff base (PA, 3.1 g). The mixture was refluxed with constant stirring with the help of magnetic stirrer for 30 min. The solution upon cooling deposited purple coloured copper complex or the brownish-orange coloured nickel complex. These were filtered off, washed thoroughly with ethanol and dried in electric oven at 80 °C and finally kept in desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂.

Preparation of heterobinuclear complexes constituting Cu^{II} metal ion and alkali metal salt of organic acids :

N,N'-1,2-Propylenebis(2-hydroxyacetophenoniminato)-copper(II) [CuPA] was taken in absolute alcohol in a conical flask and alkali metal salts of *o*-nitrophenol, 2,4-dinitrophenol, 2,4,6-trinitrophenol, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol were added to it in 1 : 1 molar proportion. The mixture was refluxed on a hot plate at 75-80 °C with constant stirring for 1-1½ h. The characteristic coloured adducts were precipitated in hot condition which was filtered, washed thoroughly with absolute ethanol, dried in electric oven at 80 °C and finally kept in desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂. For example, 1.57 g (4 mmol) of *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(2-hydroxyacetophenoniminato)copper(II) was refluxed with 0.58 g (4 mmol) of LiONP under the conditions as mentioned above to obtain 0.87 g (% yield, 75.02) of CuPA.LiONP.

Preparation of heterobinuclear complexes constituting Ni^{II} metal ion and alkali metal salt of organic acids :

N,N'-1,2-Propylenebis(2-hydroxyacetophenoniminato)-nickel(II) [NiPA] was taken in absolute alcohol in a conical flask and alkali metal salts of *o*-nitrophenol, 2,4-dinitrophenol, 2,4,6-trinitrophenol or 1-nitroso-2-naphthol were added to in 1 : 1 molar proportion. The mixture was refluxed on a hot plate at 75-80 °C with constant

stirring for 1-1½ h. The characteristic coloured adducts were precipitated in hot condition which was filtered, washed thoroughly with absolute ethanol, dried in electric oven at 80 °C and finally kept in desiccator over anhydrous CaCl₂. For example, 1.47 g (4 mmol) of *N,N'*-1,2-propylenebis(2-hydroxyacetophenoniminato)nickel(II) was refluxed with 0.71 g (4 mmol) of KONP under the conditions as mentioned above to obtain 0.91 g (% yield, 73.57) of NiPA.KONP.

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